

Robust Noise Suppression and Quantum Sensing by Continuous Phased Dynamical Decoupling

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We propose and demonstrate experimentally continuous phased dynamical decoupling (CPDD), where we apply a continuous field with discrete phase changes for quantum sensing and robust compensation of environmental and amplitude noise. CPDD does not use short pulses, making it particularly suitable for experiments with limited driving power or nuclear magnetic resonance at high magnetic fields. It requires control of the timing of the phase changes, offering much greater precision than the Rabi frequency control needed in standard continuous sensing schemes. We successfully apply our method to nanoscale nuclear magnetic resonance and combine it with quantum heterodyne detection, achieving microhertz uncertainty in the estimated signal frequency for a 120 s measurement. Our Letter expands significantly the applicability of dynamical decoupling and opens the door for a wide range of experiments, e.g., in nitrogen-vacancy centers, trapped ions, or trapped atoms.

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Developments in quantum technologies are increasingly important for multiple applications in quantum computing, quantum sensing, and quantum communication. However, decoherence remains a major challenge. Pulsed dynamical decoupling (DD) addresses this problem by using sequences of short pulses to nullify the average effect of the unwanted qubit-environment interactions [1,2]. However, the pulses should ideally be instantaneous to avoid spurious effects [3], which is challenging, e.g., due to heating at low temperatures or with biological samples.

Continuous dynamical decoupling (CDD) is an alternative that does not require strong pulses but uses a continuous protecting field and has been successfully demonstrated in multiple applications [2,4–22]. The continuous field opens an energy gap in the dressed state basis for first order noise protection, perpendicular to the field. However, the energy gap suffers from driving field fluctuations, introducing additional noise. Concatenated CDD overcomes this issue by adding more dressing fields to

iteratively compensate for amplitude noise [23]. Major drawbacks of this approach are increased complexity and limited gate speed due to the small final energy gap. Other approaches include phase modulated double drive CDD, where the continuous first field is phase modulated to mimic the effect of a noiseless second field [24], combining continuous and pulsed DD [25] or using the noise correlations between driving fields to suppress noise [26]. Robust CDD schemes are also possible in multilevel systems [12,22,24,27–30] but these typically involve additional overhead in terms of control parameters. This is often challenging due to, e.g., drift of the magnetic field or spatial inhomogeneity, limiting the coherence time especially at high magnetic fields, where small relative changes can lead to fast decoherence.

In this Letter, we propose and implement experimentally continuous phased DD (CPDD), using a strong continuous field to suppress the effect of environmental noise to first order and apply phase changes at well-defined time intervals that compensate both amplitude and environmental frequency noise errors to higher order. CPDD does not require short pulses and strong driving fields, which makes it particularly suitable for experiments that require low driving power due to temperature or setup limitations. The rotary echo protocol, where the periodic phases are 0 and π [16,20,21], is one known example of CPDD. However, its performance is not optimal due to frequency noise, e.g., at low driving fields. Windowless sequences of $\pi/2$ pulses

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FIG. 1. Experimental schemes for quantum sensing with pulsed, standard continuous, and continuous phased dynamical decoupling with signal $g \cos(\omega_L t + \xi)$. Pulsed DD uses the phases of the pulses for improved robustness but each pulse should be much shorter than the half period of the signal. CDD is applicable with $\Omega = \omega_L$ but is sensitive to amplitude noise. The phase changes of CPDD improve robustness. In contrast to pulsed DD, a uniform rectified signal is obtained for CDD and CPDD on resonance when the initial signal phase $\xi = 0$ and the phase changes are applied at intervals $T = \pi/\omega_L \approx \pi/\Omega$ for CPDD.

and composite pulses have also been applied for decoupling and refocusing of pulse errors [31–35]. In this Letter, we apply phase changes for continuous decoupling that follow robust sequences of π pulses, previously used for pulsed DD only [35–38], improving robustness to both frequency and amplitude noise.

We demonstrate quantum sensing of a signal from an external bath of hydrogen nuclear spins at low and high magnetic fields with a single NV center in diamond. We use CPDD with the phases of the popular XY8 sequence (0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) $\pi/2$ [36,39,40], labeling the new sequence continuous XY8 (CXY8). All DD protocols perform expectedly well at low field. However, only CPDD successfully detects a signal at high magnetic field as the technique is robust against amplitude errors, while imprecise control of the Rabi frequency proves detrimental for conventional CDD. Finally, we successfully combine our method with quantum heterodyne detection [41], achieving microhertz uncertainty in the estimated frequency. Our Letter expands significantly the applicability of continuous dynamical decoupling, e.g., in NV centers, trapped ions, or trapped atoms.

The system—Magnetometry experiments measure the frequency and amplitude of a signal [6,12,13,20,21]. We demonstrate CPDD for sensing of an oscillating field (see Fig. 1). We consider the Hamiltonian

$$H = \frac{\omega_0}{2} \sigma_z + \Omega \cos(\omega_0 t + \phi) \sigma_x + g \cos(\omega_L t + \xi) \sigma_z, \quad (1)$$

where ω_0 is the Bohr transition frequency, Ω is the Rabi frequency of the driving field with phase ϕ , ω_L is the (angular) frequency of the signal, g is its amplitude, and ξ its unknown phase. We move to the interaction basis with respect to $H_0^{(1)} = \omega_0 \sigma_z / 2$ and apply the rotating-wave approximation, using $\Omega \ll \omega_0$, and obtain

$$H_1 = \frac{\Omega}{2} (\cos(\phi) \sigma_x + \sin(\phi) \sigma_y) + g \cos(\omega_L t + \xi) \sigma_z. \quad (2)$$

We move to the interaction basis with respect to the driving field $(\Omega/2)[\cos(\phi)\sigma_x + \sin(\phi)\sigma_y]$ and obtain

$$H_2 = -\frac{\Delta}{2} \sigma_x + \frac{g}{2} (\cos(\xi) \sigma_z - \sin(\xi) \sigma_y), \quad (3)$$

where the detuning $\Delta \equiv \omega_L - \Omega$ and we neglect the fast oscillating terms at frequency $2\omega_L$, assuming $g \ll \omega_L$ and $\Delta \ll \omega_L$. Because of this rotating-wave approximation, the detection signal effective amplitude is $g/2 \equiv \kappa g$, i.e., it is attenuated by a factor $\kappa = 1/2$ in comparison to Eq. (2). We note that attenuation is slightly higher than that of pulsed DD where $\kappa_{\text{pulsed}} = 2/\pi$ [6]. When $\omega_L = \Omega$, known as Hartmann-Hahn resonance [42], we observe oscillations in the population of the x state in this basis with a frequency g . However, amplitude noise in Ω leads to unwanted detuning Δ that quickly causes decoherence for standard CDD [2,4–9,12–15,17,19–21,43]. Since amplitude noise is relative, its effects worsen at high magnetic fields, where stronger driving is needed to match the Larmor frequency. Achieving $\Omega = \omega_L$ is then practically impossible, leading to detuned oscillations, loss of contrast, and estimation bias.

CPDD applies phase changes in ϕ at time intervals $T = \pi/\Omega$ to compensate errors (see Fig. 1), using the phases of robust pulsed DD sequences, e.g., XY, Knill DD, or universally robust (UR) DD [35–38]. Thus, CPDD can be regarded as a sequence of phase shifted π pulses with zero pulse separation. These allow for the fastest inversion rate of the qubit, given a peak Rabi frequency, leading to a narrow band filter for environmental noise. We sense the signal field by its effect during the pulses, as opposed to standard pulsed DD. CPDD is robust to amplitude errors as its resonance condition is $T = \pi/\omega_L$, akin to pulsed DD where it is $\tau = \pi/\omega_L$ (see Fig. 1). Frequency selectivity is obtained by scanning the time interval T of the phase changes, as opposed to CDD where it is necessary to scan Ω . The Hartmann-Hahn resonance condition $\Delta = 0$ needs to be satisfied only approximately for CPDD, so errors can be compensated, e.g., Δ can be around 5% of Ω for a total duration $1600T$ (see Supplemental Material [44]).

FIG. 2. Simulation and experimental performance of CDD (CX sequence, dashed lines) and CPDD ($CXY8$ sequence, solid lines) with phase changes at $T = 62.5$ ns for a signal with $\omega_L = (2\pi) 8$ MHz. (a) Population of state $|0\rangle$ of the NV electron spin vs interaction time for different detunings Δ (shown in the legend). (b) Maximum contrast of the oscillations in (a) vs detuning Δ for CX and $CXY8$. The data for all simulations are taken stroboscopically at intervals of $0.5 \mu\text{s}$. (c),(d) Experimental data, which correspond to the simulations in (a) and (b).

We analyze the effect of errors without the sensed field. CDD applies a continuous drive $\sim \sigma_x$ [see Eq. (2)], which we label CX . Its fidelity is $F_{CX} = 1 - O(\epsilon)$, where ϵ is the typically small error in the transition probability of one π pulse, e.g., $\epsilon = 1 - \cos^2(\Delta t) \approx 0.006$ when $\Delta = 0.05\omega_L$ [44]. The fidelity of CPDD with the $CXY8$ sequence is $F_{CXY8} = 1 - O(\epsilon^3)$, which is much closer to 1.

The effect of the phase changes on the rectified signal is not trivial as only the component $(g/2) \cos(\xi)\sigma_z$ in Eq. (3) is typically unaffected by them [44]. Thus, CPDD has selectivity with respect to the signal initial phase, similar to pulsed DD [6], making it directly applicable to quantum heterodyne detection (Qdyne) [41]. Similar to pulsed DD, the signal can produce sequence-dependent spurious harmonics [3], which can be comparable to the main harmonic because the signal is sensed by its effect during the driving. Such unwanted signals can be suppressed by randomized phase changes [44], as in pulsed DD [53].

Experimental implementation—We performed experiments on two different single NV centers in diamond with an isotopically enriched ^{12}C (99.999%) layer [44]. The negative charge state of the NV center has $S = 1$ triplet ground state [54]. We used a permanent neodymium magnet to create an external magnetic field bias aligned with the NV axis to remove the degeneracy between the $|\pm 1\rangle$ states of the NV electron spin and to control the Larmor frequency of the hydrogen bath. We placed a copper wire on the diamond surface and used it to drive the $|0\rangle \rightarrow |-1\rangle$ transition resonantly, creating an effective two-level system. An arbitrary waveform generator is used for direct generation of the sequences and precise control of the phase changes. Illumination with a green laser (518 nm), used for initialization and readout of the NV spin state, reveals a spin-dependent fluorescence and favorable relaxation into state $|0\rangle$ [55,56]. All experimental details can be found in Supplemental Material [44].

First, we demonstrate the robustness of CPDD for sensing the amplitude $g \approx 2\pi 11.7$ kHz of a weak oscillating field. The results from a numerical simulation and

experiments are shown in Fig. 2. When the Rabi frequency of the driving field is equal to the angular frequency of the sensed field, i.e., $\Omega = \omega_L = 2\pi 8$ MHz, we observe oscillations of the population of state $|0\rangle$ for both CX and $CXY8$ with $P = \cos[\Theta(t)/2]$, where $\Theta = gt$. The oscillations are quickly lost with CX even with small $\Delta \approx 2\pi 20$ kHz, i.e., of the order of the coupling strength g . On the contrary, with $CXY8$ the robustness is improved by more than 20 times, as we observe oscillations even for $\Delta = 2\pi 400$ kHz [44]. The experimental results match the simulation very well with the worse performance of CDD in the experiment mainly due to amplitude fluctuations, which are not included in the simulation.

In a second experiment, we detected a nano-NMR signal from the external hydrogen bath of immersion oil with a shallow (depth ≈ 10 nm) NV center [Fig. 3(a)]. We performed the experiment at two bias fields, parallel to the NV axis: $B_z = (485 \pm 1)$ G (low field) to polarize the inherent nitrogen nuclear spin, with the Larmor frequency of the hydrogen nuclear spins $\omega_L \approx 2\pi 2.065$ MHz. Second, we applied $B_z = (1882 \pm 3)$ G (high field) where the Larmor frequency is $\omega_L \approx 2\pi 8.005$ MHz. The inherent nitrogen nuclear spin is not polarized then but the effect is negligible due to the high Rabi frequency and the decoupling sequences [57]. At low field, the Rabi frequency was roughly $2\pi 14$ MHz for pulsed DD. Hence, $(\omega_L/\Omega) \approx 0.14$, giving a good approximation for instantaneous pulses. Figure 3(b) shows the level scheme and the Hartmann-Hahn resonance condition for CDD. Figures 3(c)–3(e) show the results of three different sequences in the low field regime. In all cases the hydrogen dip is clearly visible with a difference in dip size as expected from theory [44].

At high field, the necessary shorter time spacing between pulses limited the microwave Rabi frequency to around $2\pi 12$ MHz due to heating. Therefore, we could not assume instantaneous pulses for pulsed DD. Thus, we only performed continuous drive sequences at high field. Figures 3(f)–3(h) show a dip in fluorescence due to hydrogen, which was visible only with $CXY8$, even though

FIG. 3. (a) Sketch of a shallow NV center at depth d . It interacts with the hydrogen bath on the diamond surface within a volume of roughly d^3 [58]. (b) A simplified level scheme of the NV center ground state. When $\Omega = \omega_L$ the interaction between the NV and the hydrogen bath leads to a dip in fluorescence for CX. The resonance condition for XY8 (CXY8) is $\tau = \pi/\omega_L$ ($T = \pi/\omega_L$), see Fig. 1. Experimental results for (c) DD spectra in the low field regime. The larger dip for CX is due to its longer interaction time. The label (C)XY8-N shows that the sequence is repeated N times. CXY8-16-4 denotes a CXY8-16 sequence where we did not vary Ω continuously as we varied T but it took only four values $2\pi\{1.9, 2, 2.1, 2.2\}$ MHz, demonstrating CXY8 robustness. DD order scan (d) off resonant and (e) resonant with the Larmor frequency at low field; (f) DD spectrum in the high field regime. No contrast is observed for CX even though a longer interaction time is used than for CXY8. DD order scan (g) off resonant and (h) resonant with the Larmor frequency at high field. In (h) we included the off-resonant CX plot due to negligible difference from CX on resonance, as shown in (f). The respective interaction times used in (c) and (f) are marked in plots (d),(e) and (g),(h) with gray (CX) and red (CXY8) vertical dashed lines.

we used a longer interaction time for standard CX. This is due to the better frequency selectivity of CXY8 as its control parameter is the time interval of the phase changes T . In contrast, the CX requires $\omega_L = \Omega$, depending on the microwave Rabi frequency, which suffers from amplitude noise, mainly due to power fluctuations [59]. In our experiments, the vertical resolution of the arbitrary waveform generator is 8 bit, resulting in a 30–40 kHz error in the Rabi frequency, making it practically impossible to lock the driving frequency on a signal with a frequency width of about 40 kHz. On the contrary, the CXY8 resonance condition allows a Rabi frequency error of more than $\pm 5\%$ around ω_L (see Fig. 2 and Supplemental Material [44]). Thus, the frequency selectivity is determined by the *time* digitization of the driving signal, i.e., 65 GHz, resulting in a much smaller error than the experimental requirements. We note that the broader width of the proton dip in the high field experiment is due to the larger magnetic noise and diffusion broadening [60].

Finally, we combined CPDD with Qdyne, achieving microhertz frequency uncertainty with a 120 s measurement for nanoscale high-frequency sensing. Figure 4(a) shows the scheme of Qdyne. We apply CXY8 on resonance with $\Omega \approx 2\pi 8$ MHz and $T = \pi/\Omega = 62.5$ ns. During the sequence the qubit acquires a phase, which depends on the signal phase ξ at the beginning of each CXY8 sequence [44]. The spin population is sampled at fixed time intervals T_L such that the signal phase ξ changes by a constant increment. We record individually the number of detected photons and the time of detection during the laser pulses.

The experiment takes 120 s and consists of 13.9×10^6 measurements. We perform a fast Fourier transform of the recorded photon trace and observe a signal with a beat frequency of $f_b = 19.432\,839\,1$ kHz ± 4.4 mHz [see Fig. 4(b)], which corresponds to an estimated frequency of $8\,000\,001.888\,3$ Hz ± 4.4 mHz. We achieve $\delta\nu_0 \approx 28$ μ Hz frequency uncertainty for $T_{\text{tot}} = 120$ s measurement time, which can be further reduced by prolonging T_{tot} and is mainly limited by the coherence time of the clock. The frequency sensitivity of CXY8 with Qdyne is $\eta_{\nu_0} = \delta\nu_0 T_{\text{tot}}^{3/2} = 32$ mHz/Hz $^{3/2}$ and the amplitude sensitivity is $\eta_B = (B_0/\text{SNR})T_{\text{tot}}^{1/2} = 118 \pm 8$ nT/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ [44]. These values are comparable to previous results with Qdyne [61] and can be further improved by optimizing the measurements for reaching maximum sensitivity, which goes beyond the scope of our proof-of-principle demonstration.

Discussion—The sensitivity of CPDD and pulsed DD differ by their signal attenuation factor $\kappa = 1/2$ and $\kappa_{\text{pulsed}} = 2/\pi$, respectively [see Eq. (3) and [6,44]]. The dynamic range of CPDD is similar to the one of dressed states methods e.g., continuous dynamical decoupling [6], and is 0.1–100 MHz for electronic spins or superconducting qubits [6] with the additional advantage of improved robustness. It can be expanded by incorporating a second driving field to sense gigahertz frequencies, similar to double drive continuous decoupling [23,26]. The sensitivities can be improved even further by engineering of the host diamond properties to obtain NV centers with longer

FIG. 4. (a) Scheme of nanoscale high-frequency sensing with Qdyne, using CXY8. (b) Fast Fourier transform of the photon trace to detect a signal at the beat frequency f_b , which corresponds to the signal frequency of 8 MHz.

coherence times [62,63], enhancing photon collection efficiency [44,64,65], or with ensembles of NV centers [66]. Furthermore, CPDD can be modified to perform robust quantum gates. As their speed is limited by the frequency difference of the eigenstates of the last dressed qubit, CPDD will be faster than alternative continuous robust schemes like concatenated CDD [23].

Conclusion—We proposed and demonstrated experimentally robust noise suppression and quantum sensing by continuous phase shifted dynamical decoupling. We applied a continuous driving field to reduce the effect of environmental noise to first order. Discrete phase changes at well-defined time intervals compensate both amplitude and environmental noise errors to higher order and increase the robustness of the technique. CPDD does not require short pulses and high driving fields unlike pulsed DD, making it suitable for applications with limited driving power due to thermal constraints or when high magnetic fields are required, and the Larmor frequency of the sensed spins approaches the maximum achievable Rabi frequency, rendering pulsed DD inefficient. The presented technique can also compensate for detuning and microwave field inhomogeneity in ensemble NV sensing applications. A major advantage of CPDD is that it requires control of the time intervals of phase changes, which is much easier than control of the Rabi frequency, as demonstrated in our experiments. Finally, we have shown that CPDD is compatible with high-resolution, synchronized measurement schemes like Qdyne, demonstrating quantum sensing with microhertz frequency uncertainty.

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